

After Constantine

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(June 2023)

AC

STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

Orthodox Academy of Crete

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EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

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Constantine the Great by *Chrzyśa Sakel*

EASTER RECYCLING

THANATOLOGICAL MOTIVES OF THE TEXTS OF CHRISTIANS OF THE NORTH

Nadezhda Gayevskaya*

The topic of the study is Easter recycling, as it is understood in anthropological discourse. The topic deals with the preparation for the Easter holiday in the daily life of Christian communities of the north, and the understanding of cultural memory and its symbolic expression in phenomenological discourse. The definition of recycling as symbolic processing and its definitions in culture are promising for the study of northern hagiography and culture. The analysis of the texts of the northern religious literature from the regions of Karelia and Ingermanland makes it possible to see the differences in the types of recycling, depending on the type of religious holiday, and the peculiarities of the religious life of the region.

Keywords: Easter, Christian community, recycling, inhumation, hagiography, thanatological motives, codification.

Cultural tradition finds its expression in the life of ethnic communities. In the interaction of communities, tradition is comprehended and a system is created that synthesizes norms of behavior, prohibitions and incentives. One of the traditions of Christians in the North is the celebration of the main Christian holiday of Easter. Easter occupies a central place in the topology of the Christian holidays in the north. The life of a man in the north since the X century has been focused on Easter, on the pathos of the memory of the sufferings of Christ. Easter is the main religious experience in likening to Christ, which a person is called to imitate. Easter is a testimony of the Passion and Resurrection, a remembrance of the history of salvation and a deep personal history of communion with God. The theological dimension of Easter is determined by the basic concept – the concept of memory. Memory for a Christian is the memory of Christ, the memory of deceased ancestors, and the memory as a hope for eternal life.

The central subject of experiencing feelings associated with the Easter event is the inner and existential experience of communion with God. The creative power of experiencing Easter is a spiritual aspiration to overcome the finiteness of existence because human consciousness has an inherent rejection of death, a fundamental desire to overcome it. The potential of the creative experience of Easter is represented in the idea of overcoming. In the creative energy of the holiday, penitential meanings are born: crying and mourning for sins, the fear of God and the memory of death. The memory of death, the so-called "mortal memory", as a form of God's grace, gives the experience of mortal experiences of the highest tension and opens up another dimension in the hope of a future life in eternity. Mortal memory in everyday life, in profane, for life in another world, becomes a condition for preparing for the experience of Easter. Mortal memory finds

expression in Christian rites, in the otherness of the religious. According to the Christian canon in the profane, the funeral rite opens up the opportunity to observe ritual death in the sacred space. Sacrifice unites these two principles. A sacrifice of thanksgiving and a sacrifice of forgiveness. In the space from worldly sacrifice as a behavioral characteristic to redemption through the sacrifice of Christ on the cross, the process of transformation of the memory of death as a psychophysiological characteristic into a religious strategy of mortal memory takes place.[1] Death is obvious to a Christian as a consequence of falling into sins and the finiteness of personal existence.

In the likeness of the feat of Christ, the space of thanatological meanings is revealed. Meanings find expression in the thematic motivic sphere of the hagiographic text, the main source for researchers of the life of medieval society in the North. The Easter period of society's life can be divided into three stages: the stage of preparation, the stage of the sacred cult and religious holiday, and the stage of blessing for subsequent events. Hagiographic texts convey information about pagan and Christian influences at the Easter preparation stage.

Recycling is the main element of the first stage of preparation and the central meaning of all stages of the Easter holiday: recycling of the memory of all the events of the year, renewal, and consecration of a new period of society's life. Religious rites and everyday practices function in culture as ways and options for recycling. Cultural and anthropological recycling processes are reflected in the texts, in the theme of life and death in the hagiographic narrative. The texts of the hagiography of Christians of the north make it possible to visualize the historical tradition and the evolution of forms of imprinting people's memory, knowledge, and information about local culture, one of the forms of which is Easter recycling.

Recycling is a term that means cultural processing in global civilizational and local processes. Ideas, meanings in the field of the phenomenal, rituals,

practices, behavior, attitudes, and values in the field of the real are subject to recycling. In order to study the prospects of using the theory of cultural recycling for understanding and substantiating the patterns of cultural transformations of the funeral rite of Christians of the north, recorded in hagiographic texts, we turn to the research of William Hendricks's "Three Models for the Description of Poetry" in 1969, Michael Thompson's "Rubbish Theory: the Creation and Destruction of Value" in 2017, and David Mills's "Recycling the Cycle: The City of Chester and Its Whitsun Plays" in 1998.

Hendricks writes "about recycling required in the interpretation of literary texts".[2] The lives created according to the principle of the hagiographic canon underwent artistic recycling in the process of multiplying the lists. Considering the possibility of recycling in the field of religious culture, Mills notes that "tradition" and "recycling" entered into synonymous relations explicitly and formed a single space of religious meanings, with the criterion of achieving a special religious experience and connection with the transcendent. In this, he argues with Jean Baudrillard, who justified the inconsistency of recycling and tradition but did not take into account the phenomenal properties of religious experience and the ability of religious tradition to renew. The model of three-phase cultural recycling by Thompson, which includes the phase of the initial relevance of the topic, the phase of its displacement to the periphery, and the phase of its re-return to the center, will also be in demand for analyzing the problem of recycling religious culture. Thompson divided all the subject cultural objects into several value categories. The first included those with devaluing, over time, ("transient") value, and, accordingly, a short life span, the second – endowed with "enduring"

("durable") value, that is only strengthening over time, the third, the median, were things of the "elastic region" ("region of flexibility"), not tied to the previous ones, but ready to move into them. Thompson proceeded from the fact that value qualities are not immanent to events, but are superimposed on them by society. Religious meanings are in the group of enduring value, as they are associated with the main cognitive mechanism of human consciousness in a certain period of cultural evolution, which connects them with tradition in the processes of cultural recycling. In addition, "recycling" is understood in a metaphorical sense, and it is seen as a concept with great heuristic potential. The meaning of this term metaphor is largely determined by the context, and the concept itself forms a discourse as a space of possible development.

Easter in philosophical and theological discourse can be understood as a religious phenomenon expressing the meanings of life and death, salvation, and resurrection. In the theological understanding, Easter is the memory of the sufferings of Christ. It would be more accurate to say that suffering is in the patience of the memory of Christ, which is a testimony. Easter as a holiday can be considered in anthropological discourse and expressed in material culture and the everyday life of the community. The anthropological dimension of Easter is connected with the problem of time. Time for a Christian in the middle ages was measured by the church calendar. The main dates in a person's life are the dates of the main Christian holidays. Thus, the theological and anthropological discourses of Easter unite memory and time, which are considered as symbolic concepts and are subject to cultural processing in the space of Christian meanings.

The study of cultural recycling in the life of communities in the north defines several issues. What kind of preparation for Easter did a person have in the Middle Ages, in the period from the XI to the XVI centuries? What was he doing on

holiday? What daily activities did he have at Easter and what cult activities did he do? How did Easter affect life after the holiday, and what anthropological coordinates did Easter form for the future? These questions are important for understanding the patterns of material and religious life of the inhabitants of the north.

The main source of research is the texts of Christian hagiography, i.e., the lives of saints and liturgical hymnography. Cultural and anthropological recycling processes are reflected in the texts, in the theme of life and death in the hagiographic narrative. The texts of Christian hagiography of the north make it possible to visualize the historical tradition and the evolution of forms of imprinting people's memory, knowledge, and information about local culture. [3]The analysis of the texts of the northern religious literature of the Karelia and Ingermanland regions makes it possible to see the differences in the types of recycling depending on the type of religious holiday. Phenomenological and semiotic methods allow us to study the texts of northern hagiography and identify religious meanings and the function of recycling during Easter in the region of the Christian north.

The main object of Easter recycling in the region of the north is funeral rites. To answer the question about the religious meanings of funeral rites and the recycling function in relation to them, it is necessary to consider the Christian ideas at the heart of the funeral rite.

Christian funeral rites originated in the culture of the north and developed in the period from the XI to the XVI century as a result of waves of colonization of the region and organized missionary activity: the first wave of colonization – monastic from the XI to the XIV century and the second wave – economic from the XIV century to the XVIII century. The monks, singly or in small groups, traveled huge distances through the regions of the north, in winter, without roads, dug dugouts, found caves and settled in a

completely uninhabited area. Monasticism carried out missionary work with the pagan population, founded monasteries, both cenobitic and hermit, and spiritually nurtured the vast territories around the monastery by preserving and transmitting the religious tradition. The activity of monasticism in the north received the status of a Christian feat.

Thanatological Christian meanings were brought to the north by Christians who mastered the region and Christian monasticism. History knows of two variants of the spread of monasticism in this region: monastic cenobitic and ascetic. Asceticism in theological and philosophical discourse can be considered a phenomenon that preserves a unique spiritual experience, the experience of personal transformation and spiritual ascent. Thanatological meanings are central to the religious movement of the ascetics of the north and are reflected in the texts of northern hagiography. In defining the concept of thanatological meanings, we turn to the interpretation of Bishop Kallistos Ware, Archimandrite Sophrony Sakharov, and Professor Sergei Khoruzhego. The actions and lifestyle of a Christian are aimed at achieving Christian perfections: abstinence, humility, self-denial, spiritual struggle, and dispassion.

The Christian feat is a certain existential strategy, ontological in essence, aimed at autotransformation, salvation, and achievement of personal being.[4] In the experience of the feat in the antinomy of death and life, the space of thanatological meanings is revealed. In the creative energy of the feat, penitential meanings are born: repentance, the fear of God and the memory of death. Thus, in the process of cultural transformation, the concept of death under the influence of Christianization, firstly, loses the character of a total doom and changes the temporality in commemoration and remembrance. Secondly, a new Christian axiology is being built concerning the concept of death: death becomes not an ordinary event, which is characteristic of pagan consciousness but obliges one to evaluate

one's own thoughts and actions.

Archimandrite Sophrony Sakharov writes that "being in the memory of a mortal contributes to the formation of asceticism as a cultural feat, non-possessiveness and obedience, wonderful manifestations of our love for God, chastity, and overcoming passions".[5]

Because of this, remembrance comes down to the search for the fusion of our will with the will and life of God himself. Archimandrite Sophrony distinguishes such types of memory in remembrance as mortal memory, the memory of sins, and remembrance of God. Christian thanatology is the concept of death in life, which is then transformed into mortal memory. Death becomes the essence of the Christian feat. We have to fight a lot with ourselves to achieve a complete victory over our pride. It means becoming dead to yourself.[6] In the sacred space, in parallel, we observe a ritual death, a funeral rite according to the Christian canon.

Death is necessary to the extent that it hides the everyday life in a person and reveals something else. It becomes a condition for the achievement of the feat and is thematized in life. This is a radical departure from the real, a state beyond time. Having accepted Christianity and plunged into the world of the new time, and at the same time value, mental and behavioral attitudes, the man of the north comprehended new ways to calculate time and to know themselves in time. The cultures of the north accepted the earthly time as the time of history and Eternity as a given, recognized the existence of another world, the world of the unknown, the world of the end, the world of a new being, the world of rebirth.

Space and time in the culture of the north began to be perceived and comprehended in the context of Eternity, filled with new meaning and new significance. All these processes were reflected in hagiography when in all spheres of creativity and creation, the assimilation and creation of authentic forms themselves very soon came to replace

mastering, which was reflected in the compilation of the lives of Christian saints. The problem of time becomes significant in understanding the hagiographic plot.

Episodes of the plot associated with miraculous events, with a miracle, dreams, a delusion, and prophecies can be interpreted in a temporal aspect. In the further development of the hagiography of the north, reflecting the problems of time and movement in the texts of the life, there was an increase in psychologism and aesthetic experiences, which was combined with a change in the figurative system, which was caused by the shift of the archetypal dominant: from the numinous to the human, from the sacred to the profane.

Thus, the phenomenon of the miracle found expression in visualization and the appearance of the so-called "blind spot", which is a unique modality of the phenomenal, in which the eschatological mode of the invisible is revealed. The emotional plane accompanying the sensory experiences of the heroes of the lives of the saints is also represented by "blind spots", a special kind of subjective state expressed in a frustrated reaction resulting from anxiety, fear, and horror. This is how a person in the vision of God experiences a way out of himself. The invisible as a manifestation of a miracle refers to a certain form of temporality beyond time.

Cultural models, for example the dream model sets the criteria for the aestheticization of the depicted: all the actions, thoughts and deeds of a medieval man are evaluated from the standpoint of the Christian aesthetic ideal. A prophetic dream, which also has a temporal aspect: dream images are perceived symbolically in a temporal and kinesthetic vector: as a progress through the sea of life, full of sorrows and suffering.

The experience of mortal memory and the time of being are united in the fear of God. St. Ignatius Bryanchaninov says about this: "The fear of God allows us to understand the brevity of our earthly life and the vanity of earthly acquisitions".[7]

The semantic space of "fear" is based on the opposition of the divine and the earthly. Fear is an earthly, and therefore base feeling correlated with the carnal passions of man. This is a purely physical feeling that arises in a person in moments of danger, a collision with the unknown, unclear, which struck and terrified by the power of its manifestation (perceived as fear-horror-threat). The fear of God is the fear to "offend God, to violate his holy will, the fear to lose the love of God."

Having perceived the fear of God, a person tried to live in accordance with Christian commandments. It was this desire to live according to the commandments that caused the transformation of the funeral rite, ontological meanings, and hagiographic narrative in the culture of the north. And if the earthly feeling of fear was situationally conditioned, then the feeling of fear of God was constantly present in the soul, influencing life and determining all actions in which a person relied on the fear of God as a kind of staff, because the fear of God is the beginning of all good.[8] The tense semantic space of "fear", like many other abstractions, is based on opposition and contributes to the fixation of emotional imprinting and memorization. It should be noted that the fear of God is a sure road to repentance, and mortal memory served as a means of conversion from sin. Thus, the thanatological theme, expressed in anthropological practices and theological ideas, has become the subject of cultural recycling in the region of the north. The motives of death and fear, which are part of repentance, become concepts of religious psychology: the memory of death and the fear of God. There is a development of the idea of the finiteness of existence in the Christian paradigm. All these processes were reflected in hagiography when in all spheres of creativity and creation, assimilation and creation of Slavic forms proper very soon came to replace mastering, which was reflected in the compilation of the lives of Eastern Slavic saints.

The sphere of thanatological motifs in northern hagiography is influenced not only by the Christian tradition but also by the cultural representations of indigenous peoples. In the folklore legends of this region, particularly in the legends of Chudis, the theme of death is one of the main ones. The problem of landless burials and non-burials originates in the rituals of the indigenous peoples of the north: Sami, Chudis, and Izhorians. Anthropological studies of burials in the form of grave pits in the area of ancient Chud settlements allow us to conclude that Chud buried the dead in spring and summer since in winter the earth was hidden under snow. One of the groups of rituals testifies that in winter the body of the deceased was simply left in the snow, in an open space.

It was believed that if the body was torn apart by animals, it means that a person was kind and behaved well, if the animal did not touch the body, it spoke of his unworthy life on earth. The use of log cabins and small houses of the deceased partially solved the problem of winter burials. It should be noted that the Slavs, who moved away from Christianization and mastered the territories of Karelia and Ingermanland, Zavolochye, Dvina lands in the X-XII centuries, were strongly influenced by the customs of indigenous peoples in the field of funeral rites, which was fixed in the minds of Slavic settlers in their pagan religious beliefs. Pagan ideas about burial and refusal of burial in the ground became the subject of subsequent cultural Christian processing.

The legends of Chudi's self-burial have received a special interpretation in Christian culture. The transformation of funeral rites took place in inhumation – re-giving to the earth the funeral rite. But the process of cultural translation also took place and the form of the Chudsky "houses of the dead", as well as forms derived from them, were borrowed during burials and were found in the Vazhsky district up to the XX century. It is interesting that until the end of the XX century

(expeditions of 1967, 1972 of the Ethnographic museum), when studying burials, preserved variability of ancient forms were found: tombs, log cabins, small houses of the dead, columns, cabbage rolls, shovels, roundels. Thus, ties were maintained with the culture of indigenous peoples and the traditions of Old Believers' burials. People of the old faith "Old Believers" claim that this is how the graves of those who did not receive a cross during their lifetime are marked.

The question of determining the regularities of the northern rites is a question of the geographical conditions of the area. The region to the north, from Norway, Finland, Ingermanland, Karelia to Alaska along the coast of the Arctic Ocean has unique geographical characteristics. Difficult natural conditions, cold climate, long winter, few roads, inaccessible terrain. Especially important characteristics are the beginning and end of snow melting and the opening of ice on rivers, which are the cause of very large floods in this region. The end time of snowmelt is the period from April 20 to May 15. The time of ice movement on rivers is from April 1 to May 15. This is a time of great floods.

The territory of the north is known for extensive and prolonged spring floods, which flooded vast expanses of the coasts of northern rivers. Settlements also arose in coastal areas due to the necessary proximity to water transport arteries, so floods became traditional tests for the inhabitants of the region and also influenced the formation of local culture. In particular, funeral rites and burial culture were also influenced by natural factors. So death on the road in winter, freezing in the snow, on ice, and the river became a common phenomenon, and in the spring there were many drowned during the flood of rivers.

It also washed away old cemeteries and burials, water washed out, and opened coffins that floated along rivers, moved to an unexpected place. These variants of thanatological events were subject to recycling in the form of a new Christian rite and

practice. The result of recycling is the search for the unburied and giving them to the ground, reconstruction of cemeteries and re-burials. But there are variants of mixing traditions, folk Christianity, combining pagan and Christian. One of the problems in understanding the recycling of funeral rites in northern communities is determining the function of recycling in the variant of mixing traditions.

Those who suffered a landless death, unburied according to the Christian rite, were considered taboo figures. The image of death finds its expression in the image of the deceased, which combines the sacred and the ordinary. As a result of the transformation of the previous semantic level, the deceased acquires strength and superpowers. But at the same time, it is perceived as a forbidden figure. She inspired fear in the people around her, as an unclean, dangerous phenomenon. And to bury the body in this case was forbidden by folk beliefs and traditions. Therefore, landless burials continued to arise in the region. They were the source of folk legends, fantasies, and new beliefs. Are such options a form of recycling? What is the function of the folklore and Christian component in the general mechanism of disposal?

Natural factors have influenced funeral rites and burial culture. So the stable phraseology "water has opened" and "opened with water" is used to describe the search for pilgrims, wanderers and "dashing people", "highwaymen" who died on the roads in winter frosts. The peculiarities of the northern climate determine the type of activity of the inhabitants in the region. Work on the restoration of roads, territories, and buildings destroyed by the flood is an annual practice of residents. The search and burial of those who died in winter and froze on the way, the restoration of cemeteries, inhumation, and reburial in accordance with a religious vow became the goal of pre-Easter waste recycling. Thus, the features of the harsh northern climate influenced the formation of funeral rites of both the indigenous peoples of the

Ugro-Finnish and Baltic-Finnish groups, and the Slavic colonization of the first "trade" (XI-XIII centuries) and the second "monastic" (XIV-XVI centuries) waves. They also influenced the formation of the practice of religious holidays, the Easter holiday. We can say that the most important thing for a person of the culture of the north is the period of preparation for Easter and the period of subsequent actions on a religious vow. The period consists of actions that have symbolic and ritual significance and are aimed at purification. This is the cleaning of the territory near the settlement and the cleaning of forest roads. Purification becomes a symbol of cleansing the soul of a Christian before the holiday.

The narrative contains information about the features of the harsh northern climate, which influenced the formation of the funeral rites of both indigenous peoples and Christian colonization. The legends about "not burial in the ground" and self-burial underwent a special interpretation in line with the Christian tradition. In the northern cultural code, the mythologeme of the road stands out, a sign of alienation, otherness in the pagan consciousness and wandering pilgrimage in the Christian. Death on the road became a common occurrence in the northern regions. The burial of unknown pilgrims, especially for Christian settlers, was a problem and a religious duty during the preparation for Easter. All these circumstances are reflected in hagiographic plots and the instructions of Christian bishops. One of the first instructions of Bishop Nifont: "If the bones of the dead are lying around somewhere, then it is a great merit for that person when they bury them" (1147 years).[9]

This paper presents an analysis of the texts of the hagiography of the Dvina region (the Northern Dvina River): texts about Athanasius of Navolotsky of Shenkursky (XV century), Prokopy of Ustyansk (1692), Varlaam of Vazhsky (1462), Cyril of Velsky (1450), Jacob of Borovichi (1540), John and Login of Yarengsky (1544).

The source of information about Athanasius of Shenkursky is an oral legend recorded according to the story of unknown residents: "The legend of the miracles of the revealed Saint Athanasius of Navolotsky".[10] It is known that Athanasius came to the Vaga River in the settlement "Verkhneledskoe", in the upper reaches of the Leda River, from the city of Kargopol and died three kilometers from this city on the road in the forest. The body remained unburied until it appeared in a dream to four sick people in different parts of the region, in a subtle dream they miraculously recovered, received healing, and pledged to bury Athanasius in the forest, where he died. They sang the funeral of Athanasius according to the Christian vow. They built a small wooden chapel at the burial site (1647). Miracles and healings began in this place. This place in the forest has become a center of pilgrimage. It should be noted that the nearest settlements are located 15 kilometers from the Chapel of Athanasius. In 1725, the relics were examined. It was found that the relics are intact and incorruptible.

They lie on the ground, not in a coffin. The fragrance of the relics is everywhere. Local priests opened the coffin, saw the relics intact and the funeral vestments did not decay. The name of Athanasius is included in the Cathedral of Karelian Saints, the celebration of which was resumed in 1974. The stone Church of St. Athanasius was preserved until 1950, the place where the relics lay was a place of pilgrimage for residents of the region.

The narrative of Christian hagiography is the story before Easter, the finding of the unburied body of a Christian by the inhabitants of the northern lands, the miracles and prophecies, the burial according to the Christian rite, the construction of a church on this site.

A whole group of hagiographic plots refers to the "exits from the coffin" during the spring flood. The wonderful journey became the center of the story about Kirill from the city of Velsk.[11]

The relics were kept in the church of St. Nicholas the Wonderworker in the city of Velsk. On the icons, he is depicted as a young man in white clothes standing on the bank of the Vaga River. In 1450, a rich boyar governor lived in the city. His name was Kirill. The servant drowned from the anger of the boyar. The boyar, having repented, ordered to find the body and bury it with honors in the temple. The story of finding the relics of Cyril is interesting. A young man appeared to a woman named Evlampia and said: "I was lifted up by water from the grave, and now my body lies on the bank of the Vaga. Ask them to move him to the temple and put a chapel over him." The veneration of Cyril of Velsky was widespread in the region. This caused concern of the diocesan authorities. In 1783, a meeting of the Holy Synod was held, at which Bishop Benjamin's report was heard. The Synod decided to stop worshipping the relics and not to commemorate Kirill Velsky at prayers. The canonization of Cyril should be considered the inclusion of his name in the Cathedral of All Saints, the composition of which was determined in the mid-70s of the XX century in preparation for the publication of liturgical *minas*.

One of the main problems in connection with the landless death of the blessed is the problem of official canonization, which is often expressed in the form of agreement with the fact of "popular canonization" that occurred long before the official procedure in the public consciousness. Uspensky confirms that with regard to the problem of canonization, "there is no need to talk about any established canonization procedure like that which takes place at a later time: it did not exist during this period either in Byzantium or, of course, in the Slavic lands." [12] Sainthood was expressed in canonization, but it could also be expressed in the appearance of life, the acquisition of relics, and the construction of the church.

The miraculous swimming glorified John and Longinus of Yareng.[13] Workers of the Solovetsky monastery were caught in a strong storm at sea and drowned. The sea waves washed the bodies ashore. The holy bodies were found on the Korel coast incorruptible, laid near the village of Yarenga. In the legend, we read: "The old-timers of the village of Yarenga on the shore found the remains of a man who drowned in the sea and buried him in a log cabin, in the house of the dead. After that, the saint began to appear to the locals, called himself John, and healed from serious illnesses." Miracles began to happen around the relics, which served as the basis for the construction of the monastery. We find information in the *brief legend about the appearance and finding of miracles*, about the miracles and the relics of Saints John and Loggin. The Legend is known in 4 editions compiled in the XVI-XVII centuries.

In the text of the life, we read about an interesting detail of the life of the north, namely about the standing of swampy water in cemeteries, which was common in the riverine lands. Swampy water accompanied the construction on the lowlands. This caused mass migration to higher places from the 17th century.

The body of Prokopy Ustyansky was also found at the end of the XVII century in 1692.[14] In the Kholmogorsky diocese, on the bank of the Ust River, an old coffin woven from willow twigs was taken out of the ground. In the coffin lay a body untouched by corruption, "with its head bent to one side and its hands folded not according to custom and without a shroud." No one knew what kind of person it was, whose body it was. The relics of the body revealed a miracle of healing.

Residents built a chapel and laid relics in it. It is necessary to recall the tradition of building chapels, which was called the "pominalnica". This tradition of building a «pominalnica» dates back to the pagan tradition of the Chudi people. There were very few Christian traits in this tradition. The

archbishops in the XVIII century fought against them, forbade them to build, and ordered the old ones to be destroyed. Oral traditions speak of the late Procopius as a peasant, by profession he was a shepherd, at the age of 14. At first, this name was unknown. He appeared in a dream to the villagers, called himself Procopius, and ordered to make a new coffin for himself. On August 11, 1695, by the decree of Archbishop Athanasius, the relics of Procopius of Ustyansk were examined. In the text of the testimony we read: "He was middle-aged, dressed in a shirt and trousers made of canvas." A church service has been written and performed for Prokopy Ustyansky, a new church has been built, and only a local memorial service is being held.

Death is an important archaic element in the structure of the Christian feat. The motif of death has an archetypal origin. He connects the archetypal consciousness with the image of the dead, with the otherworldly. Contact with him can lead the communicator to fatal consequences, to the rupture of his own ontology. This is one of the reasons for the taboo of the figure of the deceased by a landless death, expressed in the prohibition of the burial of the body. A person who died an unnatural death cannot be buried in a natural tradition. The natural tradition is the tradition of the Ascetic becoming an unauthorized dead man, voluntarily dying in spiritual feats. So in the image of the "bearer of death," there is a ritual figure in which the sacred is manifested.

The image of death embodied in the text of the life is endowed with great energy potential and has a strong emotional impact. Emotional memory captures fear as the main reaction to contact. The perception of this feeling is especially acute, since a person perceives himself as a sinful being, and anxiety and fear are eternal companions of the idea of the fall. Fear increases emotional tension. This means that it creates conditions for imprinting and activation of mental connections as conditions for the formation of a cultural code and memorization.

The group of texts of the northern lives includes the life of Varlaam Vazhsky.[15] During the spring flood, the relics of St. Barlaam were found. The motive of overcoming the water barrier is present as the main one contributing to the appearance of the relics of the saint. The life of Varlaam Vazhsky (Pinezhsy) relates the life of the monk to the middle of the XV century (1462). The main source of information about Barlaam was his life, written in 1589 by the hieromonk of the Antoniev Monastery, Jonah, at the request of the abbot of the monastery of St. John the Theologian. The Monastery of John the Theologian was founded by Barlaam. The buildings of the monastery have survived to our time. The Monk Varlaam was born into a family of boyars and received the name, Vasily. He received the title of tsar's posadnik – governor of the province on the Vaga River and built a monastery. It is important to note that the northern monasteries were built by lot, and the place for construction was chosen by sacred predestination. In 1456, Vasily took monastic vows with the name Varlaam and, after living in monasticism for six years, was buried near the monastery. In the oral traditions about Varlaam Vazhsky, the myth is told that the saint sailed to these lands on a raft or a stone. The place of the Monk's solitary Christian prayers and exploits is known – as Varlamyev Kolodchik, the spring surfaced.

At the well, through the prayers of the saint, a water stream appeared. In 1552 there was a great flood of the Vaga River. The mountain on which the monastery stood collapsed, and many coffins were opened, which surfaced and were brought ashore. Thus, the relics of St. Barlaam were found. The Varlamov Monastery in the XV and XVI, XVII (up to the XX century) was the central place of pilgrimage by vow for the inhabitants of the region.

Professor Olga Tuminskaya notes the central role of the image of Barlaam in religious processions, in processions to the well on the banks of the Vaga. [16]

The well is consecrated together with the image of the Sign of the Most Holy Theotokos, which goes back in the cult to the Byzantine Blachernaic tradition of the expiration of hagiiasm (holy water). Thus, a certain vector of the evolution of the sacred motif is being built: from the spontaneity of the natural northern land to the confirmation of the trial of the water element by lot, from the miraculous swimming of relics to the purification of the soul.

Hagiographic life – the life of Yakov Borovichsky refers to the hagiographic history of 1540.[17] Brief information about the saint and the beginning of his veneration is contained in the Legend of the Miracles from the relics of Jacob, presented in 3 editions. The legend of the miracles from the relics of James is based on the act of examination of the relics of the saint of July 2, 1544, on the certificate of the transfer of the relics of James of October 6, 1544, and on the act of the transfer of the relics of October 23, 1544, as well as on records of miraculous healings from the relics of the saint that took place earlier, during and after examination of relics. Blessed Jacob was a simple, diligent shipowner and fell into a cruel stupidity. He died, killed by thunder, and he was put in a wooden log «koloda» without burial. His age is young, his body is naked, only in a thin, dilapidated shirt, and his hands are folded not according to the rules. It should be noted that the naked body is a symbol of extreme poverty. The naked body endures. This is a testimony of contempt for the corruptible flesh and a sermon of spiritual exposure in approaching the sufferings of Christ. The incorruptible body was found near the village of Borovichi in the spring on the third day of Easter. The oak "koloda" stood on a huge ice floe (nakre), which was rushing in a stormy spring stream against the current of the Msta River at the formidable Borovichi River rapids. This picture goes back to the pagan rafting on the river whirlpools of sacred sacrifices. The surrounding peasants considered this mysterious appearance a

bad sign, a sign of stranger danger and pushed the "koloda" back onto the water. Having wrapped the "koloda" with ropes, they dragged the downstream on the ice and took it two kilometers away from Borovichi. Three times the "koloda" returned against the current. Until the image of the boy appeared to the elders in a dream and said reproachfully: "Why, being Christians, do you ruthlessly persecute me, a Christian?" It should be noted that the phenomenon of the holiness of the blessed is visualized as a result of dream states – acts of thaumaturgy. The relics were removed from the ice floe and placed in the chapel. Miraculous healings began at the relics. They were transferred by Patriarch Nikon to the Iversky Monastery on Valдай in 1657 after the performance of the boy's appearance in a dream to the patriarch.

The study of thanatological meanings suggests that the motive of death is revealed in parallel discourses of the sacred and the mundane. The image of death finds its expression in the image of the deceased blessed, which also combines the sacred and the mundane. As a result of the transformation of the previous semantic level, the ascetic acquires strength and extra abilities. But at the same time, it is perceived as a taboo figure. In the text of the life, we observe many pagan sacred motifs. The relics of the blessed one crossed the water barrier, which can be considered as a sacred action. The number three – Three Returns – is also associated with both folklore consciousness and Christian symbolism. The stages of sacralization prepare the appearance of the sanctity of the newly found blessed one.

The righteous Artemy Verkolsky (1545), one of the most amazing life figures, whose story served to transform the pagan foundations of the views of the inhabitants of the north about the impossibility of burial as a sacred protective action.[18] Artemiy was born in 1532 in the village of Verkola on Pinega and his parents are Kosmas and Apollinaria. Artemiy is a twelve-year-old peasant boy who was killed during a thunderstorm by the sound of thunder. It is important that the death followed

after working in the field on a holiday, which was a violation of the church rule. Therefore, it was regarded as a punishment and justification for the impossibility of putting the body to the ground. The father buried his son in the forest, putting him in a log cabin, "little house of the dead". Srubchik ([srubchik]) is a form of burial based on the Chudi pattern, common in the Dvinskoy (river Dvina) region. The relics of the boy were found incorruptible in 1577 and laid on the porch of the St. Nicholas church. Miracles and healings began around the relics.

Hagiographic texts convey information about both pagan and Christian influences at the stage of preparation for Easter. They allow us to conclude about the synthesis of influences based on ideas about life and death. Summing up, we can say that the texts "about landless death" can be divided into thematic groups: texts about missing on the road and found in the spring, reports of drowned people, a group of texts about those whose death was tabooed in pagan forms, another group of texts about those who are buried in aboveground forms: small wooden houses of the "dead", and a group of texts about "those who came out of the coffins" during the flood.

Thus, the presented biographies of the Christian northern lands, the Dvina region reveal the system of sacralization of the region, according to T. Shchepanskaya's research "crisis network" is based on the peculiarities of the nature of the region and the traditional way of life, dating back to the customs of indigenous peoples – the Chudis, Komi, and Sami.[19] The veneration of the saint took place both openly and secretly, as a vow.

Based on the analysis of hagiographic texts, it can be argued that recycling had both a religious and an anthropological character. The religious character of recycling is expressed in the form of mastering, and accumulating the meanings of mortal memory, moving towards eternal life in the daily life of a Christian. The religious component (pagan or Christian) sacralizes the parameters of

the cultural system and fixes them in cultural memory. Sacralization takes place in a cult and becomes a way of preserving tradition. Sacralization takes place within the framework of dual oppositions and is associated with the cult of ancestors, burial sites and local cult centers, and monuments of local hagiography.

The subject of cultural processing was the phenomenon of abandonment of land burial, which is associated in consciousness with the non-fixation of place and memory and not fixing death itself as an event and state. Time in the present, at the same time, here and now determined everyday life. Everything connected with the finiteness of existence was in uncertainty. Subsequently, along with Christianization, those not buried in the ground became associated with a taboo, forbidden, unclean departure from life, information about which was also in an indefinite space. Such an arrangement of information, an informative layer, performed a protective function when the knowledge of death was transferred from one reality to another. The study reveals the connection between the Byzantine tradition (acts of thaumaturgy, the Blachernean tradition of the expiration of hagiism (sacred water)), the burial rite of Northern Christians, and the thanatological motifs of Northern hagiography, forming a single unique semiosis.

Waste recycling takes on special importance before the main Christian holidays. The concept of recycling can be interpreted in a broad sense as an everyday anthropological practice of pre-holiday preparation, as well as the comprehension and development of new meanings in religious spiritual practice. Processing becomes a mechanism of renewal in a new quality, reproduction of cultural actions and meanings, thereby reproducing culture. The ability of culture to recycle is an important anthropological resource, that ensures the preservation, continuity of tradition, and reproduction of the mental code.

Christian codification used pagan codes and changed their semantic core. Burials in the form of burial in the ground, commemoration and veneration of the deceased according to the Christian rite before Easter, the appeal of residents to the Christian tradition as a protective one served the goals of economic and spiritual development of the region. Modern research shows that there was a process of cultural processing, and the existential characteristics of the culture of the region changed.

Today we can say that waste recycling is part of the tradition of religious culture. The tradition of Christian culture provides for the possibility of processing both the pagan funeral rite and the further development of the Christian rite itself, capable of transformation and performativity. In performativity, the processing mechanism is transformed into a social one, society becomes capable of cultural understanding and processing.

Notes

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[1] Tuminskaya, Gayevskaya 2021, p. 135.

[2] Hendricks, 1969, p. 1-22.

[3] Gayevskaya 2018, p. 11.

[4] Khoruzhiy 2012, p. 50.

[5] Sakharov 1956, p. 4.

[6] Svyashchennik Zabelin. Zhitiye svyatogo pravednogo Feodora. Novgorod, 1896. P. 4 // Svyatyie Novgorodskoy Zemli, ili istoriya svyatoy severnoy Rusi v likakh X-XVIII v.: V 2 t. - Velikiy Novgorod: TRIGON, 2006. / T.1. X- XV vv. P. 1-735 // Prilozheniye: Svyashchennik Zabelin. Zhitiye svyatogo pravednogo Feodora.

- [7] Bryanchaninov 1862, p. 142.
- [8] Vendina 2002, p. 334.
- [9] M.: Izd. Krug 2011. p. 544; Voprosyaniye Kirikovo arkhiyepiskopu Nifontu. p. 413-437 Available at: https://azbyka.ru/otechnik/Kirik_Novgorodskij/vo_proshanii-kirika/ [Last Access 10/04/2023].
- [10] Nikodim (Kononov) Arkhim 1901, P.22.
- [11] Romanova A. A., Ryzhova E. A. Skazaniye o Kirille Vel'skom. 2008, p. 390-442; Dmitriyev L. A. Zhanr 1972, p.192.
- [12] The canonization of saints in the Russian Orthodox Church. Available at: https://azbyka.ru/tserkov/svyatyetrubachev_kanonizatsiya_svyatyh_10-all.shtml [Last Access 10/04/2023]
- [13] «Skazanii vkrattse o proyavlenii, i obretenii, i o chyudesekh, i o prenesenii chestnykh moshchey svyatykh i pravednykh Ioana i Loggina, izhe v Yarengi novoyavlennykh chyudotvortsov». «Skazaniye...» izvestno v 4 redaktsiyakh, sostavlyavshikhsya v XVI-XVII vv. Pervaya redaktsiya 1625 g. Spiski: RNB. Solov. N° 963/1073. L. 118-134, 30-40-e gg. XVII v.; BAN. Arkhang. D. 233. L. 779-790 ob., XVII v.; GIM. Shchuk. N° 430. L. 1-16, XVII v.; RNB. Solov. N° 182/182. L. 120-126 ob., XVIII v. CHOIDR. 1884. Kn. 3. P. 12. Skazaniye o chyudesekh svyatykh Ioanna i Loggina / Izd.: O. S. Sapozhnikova // Rus. agiografiya: Issled., publikatsii, polemika. SPb., 2005. p. 579-600.
- [14] Spiski zhitiya Prokopiya Ust'yanskogo: RGIA F.796 Op. 25 D.723 (a) L.50., L.588, 597. RNB O.1.446. L. 1-13.
- [15] Spiski zhitiya Varlaama Vazhskogo: sobr. RGB F. 304. I. N° 677; 1631 g. BAN. Arkhang. sobr. D. 218 (posle 1712), RNB. Tikhanov. sobr. N° 226 (nach. XVIII v.).
- [16] Tuminskaya 2017.
- [17] Kratkiye svedeniya o svyatom soderzhatsya v Skazanii o chudesakh ot moshchey, predstavlennom 3 redaktsiyami: nach. 1561 g. RGB. Troits. F. 304/I. N° 654, 1582 g. GIM. Sin.
- [N° 447-4, 1599 g. GIM. Uvar. N° 395; RNB. Pogod. N° 1619.
- [18] Kaz. 1881, p 183-187; Dmitriyev L. A. 1973. p. 249-261, 290-292; Savelyeva N. 1999, p. 365-376.
- [19] Shchepanskaya T. B. Krizisnaya set' (traditsii dukhovnogo osvoyeniya prostranstva); Russkiy Sever, 1995.

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